

USE OF SPECIAL TENNIS EXERCISES IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES AMONG STUDENTS

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается использование специальных упражнений большого тенниса на занятиях физической культурой среди студентов высшей школы. Приводятся конкретные примеры специальных упражнений большого тенниса на занятиях физической культурой среди студентов высшей школы. Также в исследовании делается вывод о том, что при обучении и тренировке необходимо постоянно уделять внимание передвижению, действиям в атаках и защитах с сохранением устойчивого равновесия. Следует уделять пристальное внимание усовершенствованию способности восстанавливать потерянное равновесие при выполнении упражнений.

Abstract. This article discusses the use of special lawn tennis exercises in physical education classes among high school students. Specific examples of special law tennis exercises in physical education classes among high school students are given. The study also concludes that during training and training, it is necessary to constantly pay attention to movement, actions in attacks and defenses while maintaining a stable balance. You should pay close attention lost to improving the ability to restore balance when performing exercises.

Ключевые слова: большой теннис, теннис, специальные упражнения, физическая культура, физическая культура в вузе, занятия по физической культуре, упражнения.

Keywords: tennis, tennis, special exercises, physical culture, physical culture at the University, physical culture classes, exercises.

Tennis, like any other sport, the main goal in it is to bring a person to the peak of athletic form at the right moment or period. Games with a small ball, which was kicked over a net using device such as a racket. Large international tournaments attract large numbers of participants and spectators. Successful performance at major competitions depends on the coach's ability to develop and implement a long-term training plan for the athlete. To achieve results, a student must train in such a way as to simultaneously reach the peak in several parameters - technique, tactics, physical fitness, psychological attitude and proper nutrition. In addition, the medical aspects of the training must be optimized. This is an extremely difficult task facing the coach. All competitions create a situation in which short training periods are constantly interrupted by frequent competitions. When considering special tennis exercises in physical education classes among university students, it should be noted that often university coaches and teachers concentrate on competitions and victories, rather than on acquiring better skills and physical fitness, thereby underestimating the importance of training. Although today coaches, scientists and sports physicians agree that success in any sport requires an individual approach to training with a long-term perspective.

A beginner player needs to fully concentrate on acquiring and improving the skills of basic techniques and tactics in a comfortable environment. It can be said that coaches should know that long-term planning of a training regimen is the most important condition for success in sports. They should also know that for athletes, the emphasis of training, as well as its content, should change as development stages change.

To move to the next level in athlete development programs, it is believed that a critical examination of all current training and coaching methods is required. Therefore, in modern realities, a coach needs to take a close look at those methods that have proven successful in other countries or in other sports. It is necessary to pay as much attention as possible to the development of coordination skills in order to allow students at the university to devote more time to learning and practicing basic skills of technology, tactics and movements.

Agility is based on fluid motor skills. The greater the arsenal of technical means a tennis player has, the easier it is for him to master and apply new movements and actions in the game, the higher his dexterity. Of course, to demonstrate agility, a tennis player must not only skillfully master technique

and tactics, but also possess physical qualities such as speed, strength, coordination, endurance, and a keen sense of time and space. Developing agility in an athlete, as is known, goes through mastering a variety of technical, tactical skills and abilities in different situations of the game. All this, of course, leads to an increase in the stock of technical techniques of the game and has a positive effect on the functional capabilities of improving sportsmanship.

At the same time, to develop dexterity as the ability to quickly and expediently adapt during the game, exercises are used that require an instant reaction to a suddenly changing situation. It is very important that appropriate breaks for rest are provided in the educational process, because performing complex reactions in suddenly changing situations greatly tires students in university classes.

So, for example, the use of special tennis exercises in physical education classes among high school students can be considered through the prism of a certain set of exercises: make 5-15 swings with straight arms up, to the sides, or perform circular movements. Turn your head left and right, slowly and smoothly 4 to 8 times. Bend 5 – 15 times forward and to the sides, touching the floor with your palms or at least your fingertips, and make twisting movements with your body to the right and left.

In another exercise, you should take the racket by the handle. Make circles of a large radius with this hand (from the shoulder), first in front of you, then extending your arm to the side.

The game begins with a serve, which is made from behind the back line: the first - from the right side, the second - from the left, then the order is repeated. Each time the ball is served diagonally, it must hit a specific service field on the opponent's side.

A second attempt is given. After two unsuccessful attempts, the server loses the point. During one game, the same player serves. After the game is completed, the serve passes to his opponent, that is, the right to serve, to each of the players, passes through the game.

In the absence of precise coordination, the player will not be able to actively act from different positions, navigate in the face of constantly confusing factors, or quickly restore lost balance. There are many exercises aimed at developing coordination.

Of the special exercises for a tennis player, the most suitable are relay races, as well as exercises with a faceted ball.

In this regard, when using special tennis exercises in physical education classes among high school students, special attention should be paid to the development of coordination, that is, mastering the mechanics of movements, racket hits, movement, and the combination of these actions. During the game, a tennis player constantly moves quickly around the court. Movement is closely related to the transfer of body weight from leg to leg, with the movement of the center of gravity. No matter what distance a tennis player is at, he always tries to maintain balance, because the effectiveness of his actions depends on this.

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